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A Creative Folio

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Choose Peace

War is struggle.

War is trouble.

It has two colors:

Blood and ash.

It makes people hopeless.

It makes people homeless.

It steals the child's school,

the market's deal,

the elder's care.

War is a seed that grows only horrors:

Corpses. Diseases. Families scattered like leaves in a storm.

This is not a coincidence.

It is a fault of humanity.

For War happens

when these four are absent:

When Understanding is silent,

Justice is blind,

Respect is gone,

And Peace is forgotten.

It is not inevitable.

It is a choice.

We must not choose War,

but choose Peace.